

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 05.03.2021 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Prof. Devaseelan S	Chairman
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
4. Ms. Varsha A C	Member
5. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
6. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
7. Mrs. Priyadhersini. S	Member
8. Dr. Sohan Rodney Bangera	Member
9. Dr. Vrinda J Bhat	External Member
10. Dr. David Rosario	External Member
11. B Balaji Narayan	Industrial Expert

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 21.10.2020.
2. Online Class Confirmation and new features of conducting the online classes.
3. Proposal for BOS member update.
4. Discussion regarding the Value Added-Courses.
5. Approval of new program in Allied Health Science.
6. Discussion related to Ability Enhancement Courses

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 12.10.2020. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: All the department were asked to give confirmation about the online classes which was decided as per the discussion made in the previous meeting. As all the courses confirmed that the online classes were being conducted. Further discussions were made regarding the features and options available for the Online Classes. It was suggested to keep the relevant data about the online classes at hand for the documentation. The suggestion was approved by the BOS Members and all departments were requested to give updates in the next meeting.

Agenda No. 3: The Chairperson stated the importance of adding the External members to the Board of Studies. The suggestion was reviewed by the BOS Members and the decision was taken as suggested.

Agenda No. 4: As per the suggestion of the BOS regarding the Value-Added Courses, Department of Forensic Science suggested a course, “Crime Scene Investigation” and Department of Respiratory Care Technology suggested a course, “Commit to Quit Tobacco”. The resolution was taken accordingly for the Academic Year 2021 regarding the Value-Added courses and the same was approved by the BOS.

Agenda No. 5: As per the suggestion of the BOS members the new program was added in Allied Health Science from the Academic Year 2019-20 and the same was approved by the Chairman. (Reference Table 01)

Agenda No. 6: The proposal was given to add up ability enhancement courses in the syllabus. The further discussion was made regarding the same and the suggestion was approved by the BOS and all the courses were asked to update the syllabus as proposed.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Swathi Krishnan, Member and Board of Studies.

Prof. Devaseelan S,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Sciences.

Members present:

Prof. Devaseelan S

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Mrs. Swathi D

Ms. Varsha A C

Ms. Kavya Shettigar K

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